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Improving Collaborative Robotics: Insights On The Impact of Human Intention Prediction

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Abstract. This study investigates human perception and performance changes when cobots are equipped with human intention prediction capabilities. Through experiments involving a human and a cobot collaboratively solving the Tower Of Hanoi (TOH) game, three different logic (Optimal, Random and Intention Prediction) with eighteen participants. The results indicate that cobots adopting Intention Prediction logic, aiming to anticipate and complement the human move for smoother collaboration, improve the human experience while slightly reducing the performance compared to the Optimal logic, which assumes the human player always makes the best possible move. This work underscores the potential of intention prediction in advancing the collaboration between humans and collaborative robots and sets the stage for future research on adaptive and intuitive cobot.

Keywords: human-robot collaboration, collaborative robots, intention recognition, human monitoring

1 Introduction

Recently, the integration of Human-Robot Collaboration (HRC) has gained substantial traction for collaborative tasks, particularly within the manufacturing sector [9,10]. However, although there are some emerging examples, collaborative robots are still mostly used in traditional automation setups [13].

One of the main reasons for this choice is the limited intelligence of cobots, which are designed for collaboration but fail to easily adapt to different collaborative tasks. This limitation is highlighted by the lack of flexibility and adaptive behaviour in response to diverse human partners’ characteristics and changing environments. For instance, cobots struggle to anticipate and adjust to a variety of human behaviours and errors in real-time [7]. Also, system integrators usually do not adequately address critical Human Factors (HF), such as human awareness, trust, and reaction to cobots, which contribute to cobot misuse as mere automation tools [14].

To address this gap, the analysis of human reactions to cobots in collaborative tasks is of outstanding importance. Intention recognition is crucial for synchronising tasks, predicting future actions, and ensuring natural, efficient, and safe collaboration [23]. By understanding and anticipating the actions of their counterpart, cobots can adjust their behaviour to avoid conflicts and enhance task execution, marking a significant step towards intelligent collaboration [15]. Humans have the unique ability to perceive others’ actions and deduce their intentions, enabling them to perform complementary tasks. Equipping robots with similar capabilities poses significant challenges, emphasising the need for a deeper understanding of human intent and the ability of robots to adapt swiftly. However, this involves not only recognising the current actions and status of operators but also foreseeing subsequent steps.

Effective collaboration relies on the ability of both humans and robots to make synchronised decisions and predictions, making intention prediction crucial for smooth interactions in shared tasks. However, unlike measurable physiological attributes like heart rate, body temperature or blood pressure, human intent is implicitly contextual and not directly measurable. It is expressed through the human state, which comprises past and current moves, visual features and contextual information.

The research presented in this paper investigates how the behaviour and perception of humans in HRC collaborative tasks change when equipping cobots with human intention prediction capabilities. The analysis is conducted through different experiments involving a human and a cobot, jointly solving the TOH game by alternating each other. By testing three different cobot logics with a sample of eighteen participants, the analysis demonstrates that when the cobot correctly predicts the human intention and, in turn, anticipates its next move, the human perceives and experiences a better and more consistent interaction.

The rest of this paper is organised as follows: Section 2 reviews the related literature on human intention understanding and prediction in HRC. Section 3 details the logic used for the intention prediction and the experiment setup. Section 4 explains the experiment’s operational procedures. Section 5 presents the results of the experiment and, finally, Section 6 provides a sum-up of the results and outlines possible future research directions.

2 State of the Art

Over the years, several studies have been published about human intention prediction. However, to the best of the author’s knowledge, very few studies investigated the impact of human intention prediction on HF. In our context, HF is not considered as the entire discipline of ergonomics [18], which focuses on the nature of human-artifact interactions [18]. Instead, HF here refers to the study of human-related and technology-related components, including the effects of technology on the human, human on technology improvement, and human-technological relationships [12].

2.1 Human intention prediction in collaborative robotics

Human intention recognition within HRC has advanced significantly, incorporating various sophisticated techniques to enhance efficiency and safety. One prominent approach involves using hybrid recurrent neural networks that integrate improved Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) and Bi-directional LSTM networks. These models capture the complex temporal dependencies in human actions, thereby improving prediction accuracy to adapt robots' behaviour more effectively to human intentions [6]. Additionally, methods utilising probabilistic state machines have proven effective in categorising explicit and implicit intention communication, making these systems versatile across various HRC scenarios [2]. Furthermore, transformer-based models have been developed to predict human intentions early, enhancing proactive assistance and reducing response times in collaborative environments [23]. Integrating multimodal machine learning, leveraging video, audio, and haptic signals, has further refined the accuracy and reliability of human intention recognition in complex industrial settings [16]. Moreover, the Markov Decision Process has been used for predicting human intent during human-robot operations in a common workspace [11].

Another interesting approach adopted self-supervised learning for predicting user interaction intentions with service robots [1]. The method, validated in various scenarios, shows high accuracy in predicting interactions, enhancing user experience by allowing proactive robot responses.

2.2 Human Factors and Collaborative Robotics

When designing and implementing an HRC system, evaluating its quality is crucial to ensure that the system meets individual, collective, and production needs or objectives [19]. However, efforts to identify and classify factors, measures, and metrics that describe the interaction quality in the HRC domain are still difficult to discover, especially from a human-centred perspective [4]. It is easier to focus on performance-related aspects by substituting humans with more efficient machines to reach full automation rather than focus on the duo's interaction and how it can be enhanced. On the one hand, performance-centred paradigms consider robots as a means enabling the optimisation of the production process with the main objectives of improving economic benefits, focusing on aspects such as productivity, cycle time and saturation; on the other hand, the main objective of human-centred paradigms is to improve general human-well being by respecting their role, needs, job, talents, and rights.

Human reactions to collaborative robot behaviours are influenced by various factors, including emotional responses, task performance, and perceived control. Frustration significantly impacts HRC. For instance, when robots make errors during tasks, it can increase frustration and negatively affect dominance and control during the interaction [21].

A systematic research on HF used by the robotics community to assess Human Robot Interaction (HRI) systems in industrial settings reported that the

most analysed are attitudes, acceptance, mental workload, physical workload, trust mental models and awareness [4].

Structured collaborative behaviours in industrial settings are essential for balancing safety and productivity, where robots must adapt to exceptions and recover effectively to maintain efficient collaboration [5]. Adaptive leadership roles, where humans and robots shift between leading and following, also play a crucial role in enhancing trust and collaboration, as demonstrated in experiments where human participants adapted their behaviour based on feedback from robots [24]. Additionally, emotionally expressive robot behaviours can improve human-robot teamwork by making interactions more understandable and increasing the positive evaluation of the collaboration [17].

3 Experiment Setup and Logic

This work investigates how a cobot predicting and anticipating human intention can influence human perception and performance. This analysis is made through different experiments built around the collaborative execution of the TOH, being a successful game widely used in literature to study HRC [3, 15, 20, 22]

The TOH is complex from a problem-solving standpoint due to its need for strategic planning. Despite having a recursive solution, the time constraints and pressure to solve it in the fewest moves make it mentally challenging [8].

The TOH uses three vertical pegs and a number d of disks. Each disk has a hole in its center and varies in size, with no two disks being the same diameter. While it is common to begin with all disks stacked on a single post in descending order of size (largest at the bottom, smallest at the top), this initial setup is not mandatory. Any starting arrangement is acceptable if it complies with the puzzle’s rules. The objective is to transfer the entire stack to another peg, adhering to these three constraints:

- Move only one disk per turn.
- A turn involves removing the topmost disk from one peg and placing it on another.
- A larger disk must never be placed on top of a smaller one.

The puzzle is complete when all disks have been successfully transferred to the target peg, forming a complete tower.

Our study involves a turn-based approach to solving the TOH, alternating between the collaborative robot and the human participant. Participants engage with the puzzle for each experiment while the cobot employs various strategies. The game procedure follows this general structure:

1. Prediction: the cobot predicts the human’s next move $\hat{M}_{t+1}^{\text{human}}(C_t)$, leading to the potential configuration \hat{C}_{t+1} , and determines its next move $\hat{M}_{t+2}^{\text{cobot}}(\hat{C}_{t+1})$, leading to \hat{C}_{t+2} .
2. Approach: the cobot moves its gripper to the approach position $P_{\text{gripper}}(\hat{C}_{t+2})$.

3. Human move: the participant performs the move $M_{t+1}^{\text{human}}(C_t)$, changing the current configuration to C_{t+1} .
4. Optimal move: the cobot computes the optimal move $M_{t+2}^{\text{cobot}}(C_{t+1})$, leading to C_{t+2} . If the cobot is already positioned at $P_{\text{gripper}}(C_{t+2}) = P_{\text{gripper}}(\hat{C}_{t+2})$, its prediction is considered as right and it immediately perform $M_{t+2}^{\text{cobot}}(C_{t+1})$; otherwise, the cobot first approaches the new position $P_{\text{gripper}}(C_{t+2})$, then perform the move. It is worth noting that $P_{\text{gripper}}(\hat{C}_{t+2}) = P_{\text{gripper}}(C_{t+2})$ may apply even when $C_{t+1} \neq \hat{C}_{t+1}$, or $C_{t+2} \neq \hat{C}_{t+2}$ (because different moves may have the same starting rod). This could happen with the same probability within each logic.

If the human effectively takes the predicted move, the cobot will be already positioned to perform the next move for advancing the game, resulting in time-saving during the task execution. Instead, if the human performs a different move than the one predicted and the cobot is in the wrong approach position, it will have to reposition and then perform the optimal move given the actual configuration, resulting in a loss of time.

For the prediction step, three different logics are implemented:

Optimal This logic assumes the player to always go for the optimal move;³ it implements an optimal function f_{opt} that assigns to $\hat{M}_{t+1}^{\text{human}}$ the optimal move from C_t , i.e., $\hat{M}_{t+1}^{\text{human}} = f_{\text{opt}}(C_t)$.

Random This logic assumes the player to play randomly; it implements a random function f_{rnd} that assigns to $\hat{M}_{t+1}^{\text{human}}$ a random configuration \hat{C}_{t+1} (choosing among the three valid moves available at t).

Intention Recognition This logic analyses the player’s behaviours and tries to guess the next move based on it; it implements an intention recognition function f_{int} that computes the next human move as

$$\hat{M}_{t+1}^{\text{human}} = f_{\text{int}}(C(t), P_{\text{eyes}}, P_{\text{nose}}, P_{\text{right}}, P_{\text{left}}, H, N)$$

while the approach position is

$$P_{\text{gripper}}(\hat{C}_{t+2}) = g_{\text{int}}(\hat{M}_{t+1}^{\text{human}})$$

The parameters of the intention recognition function $\hat{M}_{t+1}^{\text{human}}$ are described in Table 1.

3.1 Intention Recognition Model

The Intention Recognition logic relies on a classification model realised through a multi-input Neural Network (NN). Previously described features data is provided to 3 fully connected layers interleaved by 2 dropout layers. A final dense layer

³ By optimal move, we mean the next move on the shortest path to the solution, given the current configuration.

(a) Vision

(b) Cobot in $P_{\text{gripper}}(\hat{C}_{t+2})$ before human move and participant starting the $M_{t+1}^{\text{human}}(C_t)$ move $M_{t+1}^{\text{human}}(C_t)$.

(d) Cobot starting its move given $P_{\text{gripper}}(C_{t+2}) = P_{\text{gripper}}(\hat{C}_{t+2})$. (e) Cobot completing its move.

Fig. 1: Experiment execution.

Table 1: Summary of envisioned model features

Parameter	Description	Example
$C(t)$	It represents the TOH configuration (i.e., which disks are on which rods). The example corresponds to the start configurations, where all the disks are on the first rod.	[1 1 1 1 1 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0]
P_{eyes}	Position of the centre between the eyes [x, y]	[317, 127]
P_{nose}	Position of the nose tip [x, y]	[315, 138]
P_{right}	Position of the right hand [x, y]	[378, 243]
P_{left}	Position of the left hand [x, y]	[484, 138]
H	Operator dominant hand (right or left)	[1, 0]
N	Times the participant already played the collaborative TOH	3

leads to the classification output with a softmax activation function. The NN is trained using an Adam optimiser and a sparse categorical cross-entropy loss function.

The feature selection (see Table 1) was guided by several key considerations:

- Relevance: each chosen feature directly contributes to understanding human behaviour and intent within the collaborative workspace.
- Accessibility: we prioritised features that could be reliably extracted using the existing work-cell camera setup, avoiding the need for additional sensors or equipment that might disrupt the natural workflow.
- Robustness: the selected features demonstrate consistency across various subjects and environmental conditions, ensuring the system’s adaptability.
- Computational efficiency: we focused on primary features that provide maximal information while minimising redundancy. Secondary features derived from the primary set (such as head orientation) were excluded to optimise processing.
- Non-invasiveness: our approach emphasises features that can be captured without requiring wearable devices or markers, preserving the naturalness of human movements.
- Ethical considerations: the chosen features respect privacy concerns by avoiding using sensible bio-metric data or features that could lead to individual identification.

The data collection involved 3 subjects with different backgrounds and knowledge of the game (namely expert, regular and newbie users), playing the collaborative TOH alone 3 times each, using the setup of the experiment (i.e., vision system, TOH’s rods and disks positions, workbench and chair’s height). This resulted in a comprehensive dataset that accurately reflects the conditions of our experiment. We then processed this raw data, elaborating on key aspects and encoding relevant features. This refined dataset served as the foundation for

training our Intention Recognition model, ensuring its relevance and applicability to the specific collaborative robotic scenario we’re addressing.

The trained model achieved a test accuracy of more than 95% and can eventually predict the operator moves even when they deviate from the optimal sequences.

Our system predicts and determines the cobot’s approach once per move, immediately after completing its previous action and before the human’s next move ($\hat{M}_{t+1}^{\text{human}}$). This means we consider contextual human features at a single point in time, which may not fully represent the human’s state throughout the entire interaction.

A potential enhancement would be continuous prediction and dynamic adjustment of the cobot’s approach until humans move. However, we chose not to implement this for three key reasons:

- Limited impact of contextual features: testing revealed that contextual human features had minimal influence on the model’s predictions in this specific scenario. When comparing two sub-models, one using only the configuration array and another using only contextual human features, the former performed nearly as well as the full model, while the latter’s performance was unsatisfactory. This suggests that continuous predictions would rarely alter the cobot’s approach.
- Fairness in comparative analysis: the Optimal and Random approach logic uses a single approach per cobot move. Implementing multiple approaches for the Intention Recognition logic would create an uneven comparison. While the random logic could potentially be adapted, the optimal logic inherently produces a single, consistent outcome.
- Potential for human confusion: we hypothesize that a cobot making multiple approach adjustments during a human’s move might confuse or disturb the human operator. However, this is a supposition that warrants further investigation in future studies.

Our approach balances practical considerations with the need for fair comparison and human-centric design while acknowledging areas for potential future research.

4 Experiment Protocol

The experiment protocol involves four distinct phases:

1. Introduction to the experiment: it consists of a short briefing explaining the experiment objectives, the TOH and its rules. The participant is also informed that the cobot will make predictions about their moves and that it can fail.
2. Initial data collection: it includes a series of multiple choice questions related to the previous experience with the TOH, with collaborative robots, and the expectations to work with a cobot in an intention prediction scenario. Moreover, H and N are collected, to configure the experiment setup.

3. Execution of the experiment through three TOH rounds applying in random order the 3 logic: all the six permutation of the set $\{1, 2, 3\}$ ⁴ were organized, each one played by 3 participants.;
4. Final data collection: it consists of the remaining multiple choice questions from the questionnaire, which are mainly needed to assess participants' feelings and opinions about the experiment and the collaboration with the cobot in the different game modalities.

5 Results

A sample of eighteen participants played the collaborative Tower Of Hanoi with all the different logic. Ten participants had already played the TOH, and seven had interacted with a cobot before the experiment. All participants were informed that the collaborative robot would anticipate their move and could be wrong. No information was provided about which logic was implemented in each round.

From a productivity point of view, analysing the box and whisker plot of Figure 2, it is clear that Random logic has more data outside the interquartile range, indicating more variability than Optimal and Intention Prediction logic. The smaller interquartile range and lower median in the Optimal logic indicate that this approach is more consistent and efficient, leading to fewer outliers and more predictable performance. This consistency is crucial for collaborative robotics, where predictable behaviour can significantly enhance workflow and reduce task execution times. Furthermore, Optimal logic has a lower median, and data is more concentrated, as the box sizes show. The other logic's performance was slightly worse, but it's important to consider that the actual cobot move always follows the Optimal strategy, and sometimes the cobot may undo the participant's move, resulting in longer execution sequences and time.

Intention Prediction logic, while not as tightly concentrated as Optimal logic, still shows less variability than Random logic. This suggests that even when not perfectly accurate, predicting human intentions provides more stable performance, reducing the variability that comes with entirely random actions. This balance between predictability and adaptability makes Intention Prediction logic a viable approach for improving collaborative tasks.

Figure 3 confirms this, showing that the participants enjoyed more the experience in Intention Prediction logic compared to Optimal logic, showing a higher median and less variability.

In Figures 4 and 5, Random logic's box plots confirm that the user tends to ignore cobot moves (low influence) since the different prediction usefulness and influences are comparable among the logic. Some participants have confirmed that they weren't even looking at the cobot approaches, while others were basing their moves on the cobot behaviour.

⁴ 1=Optimal approach; 2=Random approach; 3=Intention prediction

Figures 3 and 4 highlight that the participants appreciated the Intention Prediction logic more, probably because it was better at predicting their intentions and enabling a fluid collaboration experience.

Fig. 2: Game execution time

Fig. 3: Prediction experience

Fig. 4: Prediction usefulness

Fig. 5: Prediction influence

We analysed the Intention Prediction model’s incorrect predictions of human moves (Figure 6) and the Optimal logic’s non-optimal human moves (Figure 7). The latter also reflects the number of incorrect predictions made by the Optimal logic. Our analysis supports our hypothesis: the Intention mode performs better in predicting human moves than the Optimal logic. This is likely because most players tend to make errors, and the Intention Prediction model can predict these mistakes, enabling the cobot to anticipate them.

Analysing Figure 7 is that, in these experiments, the number of non-optimal human moves was distributed similarly among the different rounds in each game modality. This could be another confirmation that the cobot approaches do not influence the player much.

This work provides insights into human behaviour in executing collaborative tasks with a cobot and a few relevant starting points to be further explored soon.

Discussing limitations, we must mention the single use case where this experiment was conducted. In the Tower Of Hanoi, the predictions are always limited to valid moves at each game step. That is probably why the past execution sequences are more important than human-related features (e.g., hand position).

Fig. 6: Wrong predictions

Fig. 7: Non-optimal moves

The application in other use cases suggested that the higher the variability of a sequence of tasks, the higher the relevance of the human features. Moreover, as anticipated in Section 3.1, our approach involved single-time-point predictions, which may not fully capture the dynamic nature of human intent. Continuous predictions will allow us to exploit the model’s full potential, adapting the cobot behaviour and approach in real-time.

Finally, although the cobot used different logic for its approach, its actual move was always optimal. We made this choice to ensure a fair comparison between the three logic and to guarantee that the game would reach completion in a reasonable amount of time. However, this approach has a drawback: particularly with the Intention Prediction logic, sub-optimal sequences generated by the model cannot be explored, as the cobot will always follow the optimal move, regardless of the human’s intention.

6 Conclusions

This study explored the impact of human intention prediction on HRC by examining how different human move prediction strategies and consequent cobot approaches affect human perception and performance in collaborative tasks. Specifically, we implemented and tested three distinct logic: Optimal, Random, and Intention Prediction, during a collaborative TOH with eighteen participants.

Our findings reveal several insights. The Optimal logic demonstrated the highest consistency and efficiency, marked by fewer outliers and more predictable performance. Moreover, participants reported higher satisfaction and perceived better collaboration with the Intention Prediction logic compared to the other logic. The ability of the cobot to predict and anticipate human moves contributed to a more fluid and natural interaction, despite not being perfectly accurate. This balance between adaptability and predictability positions the Intention Prediction logic as a promising approach for improving collaborative tasks. The study also highlighted that some participants tended to ignore cobot moves, underscoring the importance of a more structured and predictable interaction. Participants showed improvement in performance across different rounds, regardless of the

cobot logic used. This suggests that experience and familiarity with the task contribute significantly to better performance, emphasising the need for adaptable and intuitive cobot strategies that can accommodate varying levels of human expertise.

Our future research will target a broader spectrum of collaborative tasks and environments. This aims to validate current findings and further explore the potential applications and effects of intention prediction. Additionally, we plan to examine the influence of new input features for our models, such as human performance metrics and emotional and behavioural responses. The final phase of our research will focus on developing an adaptive logic. This system will be capable of dynamically switching between different logical approaches based on real-time human performance and feedback, ultimately leading to an enhanced collaborative experience.

References

1. Abbate, G., Giusti, A., Schmuck, V., Celiktutan, O., Paolillo, A.: Self-supervised prediction of the intention to interact with a service robot. *Robotics and Autonomous Systems* 171, 104568 (2024), <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0921889023002075>
2. Awais, M., Henrich, D.: Human-robot collaboration by intention recognition using probabilistic state machines. 19th International Workshop on Robotics in Alpe-Adria-Danube Region (RAAD 2010) pp. 75–80 (2010)
3. Charisi, V., Gomez, E., Mier, G., Merino, L., Gomez, R.: Child-robot collaborative problem-solving and the importance of child’s voluntary interaction: a developmental perspective. *Frontiers in Robotics and AI* 7, 15 (2020)
4. Coronado, E., Kiyokawa, T., Ricardez, G.A.G., Ramirez-Alpizar, I.G., Venture, G., Yamanobe, N.: Evaluating quality in human-robot interaction: A systematic search and classification of performance and human-centered factors, measures and metrics towards an industry 5.0. *Journal of Manufacturing Systems* 63, 392–410 (2022)
5. Ding, H., Heyn, J., Matthias, B., Staab, H.: Structured collaborative behavior of industrial robots in mixed human-robot environments. 2013 IEEE International Conference on Automation Science and Engineering (CASE) pp. 1101–1106 (2013)
6. Gao, X., Yan, L., Wang, G., Gerada, C.: Hybrid recurrent neural network architecture-based intention recognition for human–robot collaboration. *IEEE Transactions on Cybernetics* 53, 1578–1586 (2021)
7. Gorur, O.C., Rosman, B., Sivrikaya, F., Albayrak, S.: Fabric: A framework for the design and evaluation of collaborative robots with extended human adaptation. *ACM Transactions on Human-Robot Interaction* 12, 1 – 54 (2021)
8. Hinz, A.M., Klavžar, S., Milutinović, U., Petr, C.: *The tower of Hanoi-Myths and maths*. Springer (2013)
9. Keshvarparast, A., Battini, D., Battaia, O., Pirayesh, A.: Collaborative robots in manufacturing and assembly systems: literature review and future research agenda. *Journal of Intelligent Manufacturing* pp. 1–54 (2023)
10. Liu, L., Guo, F., Zou, Z., Duffy, V.G.: Application, development and future opportunities of collaborative robots (cobots) in manufacturing: A literature review. *International Journal of Human–Computer Interaction* 40(4), 915–932 (2024)

11. McGhan, C.L., Nasir, A., Atkins, E.M.: Human intent prediction using markov decision processes. *Journal of Aerospace Information Systems* 12(5), 393–397 (2015)
12. Meister, D.: The history of human factors and ergonomics. Lawrence Erlbaum Associates Publishers (1999)
13. Michaelis, J.E., Siebert-Evenstone, A., Shaffer, D.W., Mutlu, B.: Collaborative or simply uncaged? understanding human-cobot interactions in automation. In: *Proceedings of the 2020 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*. pp. 1–12 (2020)
14. Montini, E., Cutrona, V., Dell’Oca, S., Landolfi, G., Bettoni, A., Rocco, P., Carpanzano, E.: A framework for human-aware collaborative robotics systems development. *Procedia CIRP* 120, 1083–1088 (2023), <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2212827123008612>, 56th CIRP International Conference on Manufacturing Systems 2023
15. Montini, E., Ploner, G., Matteri, D., Cutrona, V., Rocco, P., Bettoni, A., Pedrazzoli, P.: Impact of collaborative robots on human trust, anxiety, and workload: Experiment findings. In: *Advances in Production Management Systems*. Springer Nature Switzerland, Cham (2024), pre-print available at <https://shorturl.at/bn21O>
16. Ni, S., Zhao, L., Li, A., Wu, D., Zhou, L.: Cross-view human intention recognition for human-robot collaboration. *IEEE Wireless Communications* 30, 189–195 (2023)
17. Novikova, J., Watts, L., Inamura, T.: Emotionally expressive robot behavior improves human-robot collaboration. 2015 24th IEEE International Symposium on Robot and Human Interactive Communication (RO-MAN) pp. 7–12 (2015)
18. Salvendy, G., Karwowski, W.: *Handbook of human factors and ergonomics*. John Wiley & Sons (2021)
19. Verna, E., Puttero, S., Genta, G., Galetto, M., et al.: A novel diagnostic tool for human-centric quality monitoring in human-robot collaboration manufacturing. *Journal of Manufacturing Science and Engineering* 145(12), 121009 (2023)
20. Wainer, J., Feil-Seifer, D.J., Shell, D.A., Mataric, M.J.: The role of physical embodiment in human-robot interaction. In: *ROMAN 2006-The 15th IEEE International Symposium on Robot and Human Interactive Communication*. pp. 117–122. IEEE (2006)
21. Weidemann, A., Rußwinkel, N.: The role of frustration in human–robot interaction – what is needed for a successful collaboration? *Frontiers in Psychology* 12 (2021), <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/psychology/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.640186>
22. Wright, L.L., Kothiyal, A., Arras, K.O., Bruno, B.: How a social robot’s vocalization affects children’s speech, learning, and interaction. In: *2022 31st IEEE International Conference on Robot and Human Interactive Communication (RO-MAN)*. pp. 279–286. IEEE (2022)
23. Zhang, X., Tian, S., Liang, X., Zheng, M., Behdad, S.: Early prediction of human intention for human-robot collaboration using transformer network. Volume 2: 43rd *Computers and Information in Engineering Conference (CIE)* (2023)
24. Zoelen, E.V., Barakova, E., Rauterberg, G.: Adaptive leader-follower behavior in human-robot collaboration. 2020 29th IEEE International Conference on Robot and Human Interactive Communication (RO-MAN) pp. 1259–1265 (2020)